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Local Government Autonomy and the Urban Political Settlement: Implications for Resilient Cities in Lagos, Nigeria.

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Abstract:

Strengthening local governance is crucial to building resilient communities in African cities that face climate vulnerabilities, infrastructure strain, and inequalities. In Lagos, local government authorities often lack the autonomy needed for effective WASH and climate adaptation service delivery. This study examines how political settlements shape local government autonomy and influence reform coalitions for urban resilience. We conducted a desk-based pre-study that combined secondary data, ACRC domain findings on WASH, climate resilience, and street lighting, as well as legal frameworks and policy reports. Applying the ACRC political settlements framework, we mapped elite group configurations, resource allocation dynamics, and service delivery outcomes. Despite constitutional provisions for local autonomy, elite bargains in Lagos prioritize control and rent distribution, weakening local governments. Fragmented responsibilities, fiscal dependence, and politicized decision-making undermine long-term WASH and climate infrastructure resilience, sidelining community needs to maintain elite consensus. Effective reform requires coalitions grounded in urban political realities, integrating marginalized actors, civil society, and reform-minded bureaucrats to sustain resilience-enhancing policies.

Keywords: Local Government Autonomy; Political Settlements; Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH); Climate adaptation, Streetlighting

Main highlights:

- Lagos LGAs lack real autonomy for WASH, climate adaptation and streetlighting.
- Elite bargains centralize control and weaken local governance.
- Fiscal dependence and fragmented mandates harm resilience.
- Politicized project siting sidelines community needs.

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- Reform coalitions must unite civil society, bureaucrats, and donors.
- Sustainable change requires engaging with urban political dynamics.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation Meaning

ACRC	African Cities Research Consortium
FSD Africa	Financial Sector Deepening Africa
LCARP	Lagos State Climate Adaptation and Resilience Plan
LGAs	Local Government Areas
LWC	Lagos Water Corporation
NGO(s)	Non-Governmental Organization(s)
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
WASH	Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene

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Introduction

Much pressure continues to mount on Nigeria's most populous city-Lagos, from rapid urbanisation, climate change, and widening infrastructural deficits. According to Adewumi (2024), Lagos saw an increase of about six hundred thousand people within one year between 2023 and 2024. Such rapid population growth has created a strain on existing infrastructure, and challenges of environmental degradation, traffic congestion, absence of adequate housing and crime rate increase (Adewumi, 2024). From serious flooding and sanitation challenges to a worsening state of public services like street lighting, Lagos has seen them all, and the city's growing vulnerabilities continue to threaten its functionality and adequacy for living. According to the African Cities Research Consortium (ACRC) (2023), the crime rate and need for emergency management in Lagos have gone so far as discouraging the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), while also creating severe challenges to public safety and security.

In conversations surrounding these problems and how they could be solved, much attention has been on possible technical solutions and master plans, but less scrutiny has been given to the political structures that shape how decisions are made and the power blocs that control urban resources. For instance, Abiodun (2019) speaks of how the preventive measures put in place in order to protect the Lagos environment have been weak and unsustainable. Instead, successive administrations have adopted the fire brigade approach, which is even worsened by challenges of indiscipline, corruption, official mendacity, and lethargic reactions from the government. Specifically, the limited autonomy of local governments, which is understood to be the closest level of government to the people, raises urgent questions about the governance of important services and urban resilience.

Despite Nigeria's federal structure and constitutional provisions that establish local governments as the third tier of government, local authorities in Lagos are practically political subordinates to the state government. Their fiscal capacity is weak, their mandates are often unclear or duplicated, and their leadership is frequently a reflection of dominant party structures. As Uduku & Lawanson (2022) puts it, Lagos' local government system is extremely incapacitated, with informal governance institutions taking their place in influencing everyday life. Their elections, just like it is across board in Nigeria, are seen as a zero-sum game for the

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ruling party in the state, according to Olaleye (2023). This governance setup reflects a deeper political settlement in which power is negotiated and controlled by elite actors who prioritise centralisation and patronage over decentralisation and accountability within the city.

This article examines how political settlements in Lagos shape the limitations and possibilities of local government autonomy in important domains at the core of resilient urban development. The article attempts an investigation into how elite bargains and institutional arrangements constrain or enable local governments to contribute to urban reform in sectors like WASH, climate adaptation, and street lighting. The article explores how these sectors reflect the broader trends in urban governance within Lagos and identifies potential pathways for reform-oriented coalitions within the political context.

Political Settlements and Urban Governance in Lagos

Political settlements refer to formal and informal agreements between powerful groups, which determine how power and resources are distributed in a society. Kelsall et al., (2022) define it as an ongoing agreement among the most powerful groups within a society, concerning certain political and economic institutions which can expectedly generate a level of benefits for them. From the most pragmatic perspective, political settlements are conceived as coercive and patriarchal. These settlements are seen as products of ‘horse-trading’ processes whereby actors make ‘exclusionary’ deals ‘under the table’ (Conciliation Resources, 2015). Political settlements are dynamic arrangements that are shaped and reshaped from time to time by how elites struggle over access to state institutions, rents, and legitimacy.

In Lagos, the urban political settlement is characterised by a highly centralised model of governance, whereby power is concentrated at the state level. According to Obisanya & Hassan (2022), the Lagos State government still holds the purse strings, and only disburses the funds that can cover the running costs of the local government bodies in the state. At the same time, various kinds of gazettes, policies, and laws are churned out every day within the state, in a bid to take over revenue collection and other statutory functions from local governments, amidst other things done as a means of exercising excruciating state control on the local government. Local government chairpersons are often selected or heavily influenced by party structures that align with the state governor, and this makes them politically dependent, rather than having

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autonomy as political actors. Rather than be engines of grassroots development, local governments often serve as vehicles for patronage and political mobilisation.

In this framework, elite consensus and political calculations shape the distribution of infrastructural projects, political appointments, and even service delivery priorities, more than proper local needs assessments or participatory planning. This is why governance outcomes, particularly in sectors like WASH, climate resilience, and street lighting, are undesirable. For instance, Pillah (2024) discusses the sad reality for local governments in Nigeria, with no exception to Lagos state, where local authorities can not make autonomous decisions on their developmental needs. The manner in which these issues are handled usually reflect the interests of the political actors negotiating the settlement, rather than the communities actually affected by policy failure. This political logic supports the narrative that many well-crafted urban plans and policies in Nigeria stall when they get to the implementation phase. In situations where powerful political actors perceive that city reforms can threaten their established benefits, they quietly resist or selectively implement these reforms.

Domain Analysis: WASH, Climate Resilience and Street Lighting

Using the African Cities Research Consortium (ACRC) political settlements framework, the domains of WASH, climate resilience, and street lighting, give concrete illustrations of how elite bargains that constrain local government autonomy shape urban governance in Lagos.

a. WASH

WASH is important for public health, economic productivity, and environmental sustainability, according to Samuel (2023). In Lagos, however, water supply and sanitation services show signs of a highly centralised governance structure that sidelines local governments. The Lagos State Water Corporation (LSWC) maintains control over piped water infrastructure, funding, and major expansion projects, according to the Lagos State Ministry of Environment and Water Resources. Different ministries, parastatals, and private contractors handle sanitation services. The formal mandate for local governments regarding environmental sanitation has largely been reduced to organising clean-up exercises from time to time, enforcing minor public health bylaws, or issuing waste disposal licenses on a small scale. They lack the fiscal and legal space to plan or execute meaningful WASH projects. It is an avid representation of what Samuel et al., (2021) explains as a key challenge of cities in Nigeria, with the majority of their dwellers lacking access to safe water and sanitation. Such a situation indicates that the capacity of local

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governments is becoming weaker at galvanizing local actions for efficient provision and management of key services at community levels. In fact, most policies and programmes of government usually seem to overlook the roles of local governance and local government in the provision and governance of WASH at the community level. The cost of this arrangement is borne by residents. Many communities, especially in semi-urban and informal settlements, rely on boreholes, sachet water, and informal pit latrines (Longe & Yaya, 2015). Local government environmental health officers are not properly integrated into state-level WASH infrastructure planning, thereby further entrenching inequality. Without proper autonomy, local governments cannot tailor their interventions to the needs of residents or respond quickly to public health risks.

b. Climate Resilience

Lagos' coastal and low-lying geography makes it one of Africa's most climate-vulnerable megacities, with instances of flooding, sea-level rise, and storm surges being yearly realities that disrupt livelihoods and cause billions in damages. According to Ndimele et al., (2024), Lagos ranked 30th out of 136 port cities in terms of the extent to which the population is exposed to flooding, based on a past climate scenario (2005). The state also ranks 15th in exposure to flooding, based on a future climate scenario (2070s). FSD Africa (2025) leverages on advanced climate analytics to assert that Lagos' sea levels is projected to increase by up to 3 meters by 2050, with temperature rising by +1°C, and up to 4 meters of flooding as a result of extreme rainfall. With all of these happening, doing nothing or nothing much about these three climate risks is approximately projected to cause a loss of about \$40 billion by 2050, leaving physical, social, and economic systems impacted. Over 1.4 million people in the city face direct risk from flooding, as a matter of fact.

Meanwhile, effective climate resilience requires coordinated infrastructure maintenance and the promotion of nature-based solutions. Basically, local governments should play a leading role in these adaptation efforts because they are the closest to the communities affected, can maintain drainage channels, and are able to integrate climate resilience into decisions on the use of land. As Reisinger et al., (2011) infers from their study of New Zealand, an enabling environment for local governments in climate resilience is one where they get to do the job of raising awareness of climate change within the community, as they engage and develop the

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local expertise of professionals and decision-makers by presenting the science, scenarios and uncertainties of climate change in contexts that are relevant to their local communities. It is also local governments who are meant to adopt a sequential approach that can help in risk assessment and identification of vulnerabilities in the context of other pressurizing factors in the socioeconomic sphere and within their various locations, while enjoying support from the central government through regulation and guidance material.

In reality however, these functions are yet again entirely absorbed into centralised state projects. The Lagos State Climate Adaptation and Resilience Plan (LCARP) of 2024 for instance, contains extremely beautiful and well-crafted ideas which if implemented, will boost the state's climate resilience by miles. However, it also puts local governments as mere beneficiaries of the projects to be carried out, with little or no chance given to local authorities to share in the 'doing'. The political settlement logic behind this is one where large-scale climate projects attract donor funding, public visibility, and substantial contracting opportunities, thus making them politically and commercially valuable to the state government. Devolving these to local governments risks diluting control over these benefits by elites.

c. Street Lighting

Street lighting is often seen as a basic local service, just as Ojukwu (2025) calls it the preserve of the local government. That is, formally, local governments are responsible for installing and maintaining streetlights within their jurisdictions. In Lagos, procurement and installation have however been centralised, as they are handled by state ministries or outsourced to contractors with political connections. A good instance is the most recent deployment of 22,000 solar streetlights by the Lagos state government, according to a Punch report by Olawin (2024). It becomes a challenge that the choice of where streetlights are placed often reflects political visibility rather than safety needs, with more focus being on high-traffic areas, central business districts, or places that are politically strategic. According to Badiora (2025), Lagos has an extreme deficit of streetlights, with most of the roads in the residential areas dark. In places where there are public streetlights, many of them are no longer functioning, while others are gradually declining due to how long they've been used and how poorly they've been maintained. Worse still, informal settlements are most often excluded from this service, with many of their areas never experiencing such light, despite the fact that a significant portion of the city's population reside there. Over 200 of such communities are in Lagos (Badiora, 2025).

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Badiora (2025) explains the reason for this to be how the provision and maintenance of streetlights by the state sometimes is related to patronage politics or client politics, which they use to garner the votes of communities and their residents, or to reward some form of political support they had previously shown. Informal settlements on the other hand do not usually have that capital and political pull to attract infrastructural projects like these, unlike those areas where the elites in the city reside. Hence, in their ACRC report, Badiora (2025) found that the provision of streetlight infrastructure is narrowly concentrated and oriented to benefit the neighborhoods of elites. This kind of politicisation undermines equitable service provision, with low-income communities often remaining in darkness, and having challenges of public safety, gendered risks, and night-time economic activity. Local governments are unable to allocate their own lighting budgets, meaning they cannot address these disparities without state approval.

From a political settlement perspective, these kinds of arrangements observed from the three domains serve elite interests. They illustrate Wilfahrt (2018)'s view that local government performance is usually determined by elites' relations among each other within their local communities. That is, it is only when cohesion among elites is produced from ties they share with their local communities, that individual opportunism reduces and local government performance improves. The type of arrangement existing in Lagos concentrates the authority to procure and control revenue streams in state-level institutions, where contracts can be awarded to firms that are connected politically to the elites. Capital-intensive projects in these sectors then become prime opportunities for rent distribution among influential actors within the state. This political economy makes it undesirable to devolve that control to local governments who are meant to be more responsive to community demands, since they are less useful for maintaining elite bargains. This is why Wang (2023) argues that centralisation as a system reduces the provision of public goods and services, especially the ones that involve greater local government activity.

Discussion of Findings

The evidence gathered from the WASH, climate resilience, and street lighting case domains reveals that local governments in Lagos operate within a political settlement that systematically constrains their autonomy, not just as determined by administrative weakness, but more as a product of deliberate elite bargains. These manifest as follows:

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- a. The Nigerian constitution assigns clear responsibilities for service delivery, especially in the sectors of environmental sanitation, local infrastructure, and public health, to local governments. However, in Lagos, the practical authority to design, finance, and implement these services is retained at the state level. Under the political settlements framework, such maintenance of fiscal and operational dependence of local government allows state-level elites to control allocation of lucrative contracts for infrastructure works, direct resources to politically strategic areas, and use local governments as extensions of party machinery instead of their function as politically-autonomous agents.
- b. Service delivery becomes a vehicle for rent distribution, whereby capital-intensive urban projects provide steady opportunities for rent extraction through the procurement and allocation of such projects. Under the political settlement dominant in the city, these rents are not widely dispersed. Rather, they are concentrated among a tight circle of politically connected contractors, bureaucrats, and political patrons. Hence, retaining project control at the state level therefore becomes rational within this settlement, as the devolution of authority to local governments puts such controlled distribution of rents at risk. Even when such projects enjoy donor or federal funds, state-level gatekeeping still ensures that the resources pass through channels that reinforce cohesion among elites.
- c. Fragmented and politicised decision-making weakens urban resilience in Lagos, considering that urban resilience requires such type of planning that is integrated, predictable, and needs-driven, especially in WASH and climate adaptation. Politicised siting of projects prioritises areas of electoral interest over areas that need them the most, and there is a higher tendency of such projects to be short-term, as they serve as campaign symbols rather than components of long-term strategies for resilience.
- d. Local governments are implementers, not innovators. In situations where local governments do actually have meaningful contributions, it is usually in projects that are more labour-intensive and with low cost, such as street cleaning drives, community sensitisation, or small repairs, and they are often under the branding of state initiatives. With local government lacking independent budget lines, and clamped down by restrictive state oversight, they are stripped of the capacity to innovate or foster community-based resilience measures. This further creates the problem of poor local legitimacy whereby residents can not view their local councils as capable of effecting change.

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e. These aforementioned issues imply that any strategy targeted at strengthening local government autonomy must first contend with the political reality that the existing settlement benefits power blocs. Hence, technical reforms like legislative amendment or increase in budgetary allocations are unlikely to give lasting solutions, unless they are backed by reform coalitions that align with, or reshape, the incentives of the elites. Such coalitions can comprise reform-minded bureaucrats within the state machinery who see the long-term value in investing in the city's resilience, civil society organisations and community-based groups that can mobilise public pressure, as well as external actors (donors, private sector partners) that can link funding to genuine participation of local authorities.

Conclusion

Using a desk-based review of the ACRC domains on WASH, climate resilience, and street lighting, the study found that Lagos' existing local governance structure is less of a product of institutional weakness and more of a deliberate configuration of elite power bargains, whereby the statutory responsibilities granted to local authorities by the constitution are overridden in practice by mechanisms of fiscal control, project gatekeeping, and politicised resource allocation at the state level. The political settlement in Lagos prioritises elite consensus, rent distribution, and political stability over the devolution of authority and long-term service resilience. Due to this, LGAs remain dependent implementers rather than autonomous actors that can innovate or sustain their investment in resilience infrastructure.

The dynamics of these findings undermine resilience in various ways - fragmenting service delivery responsibilities, distorting project siting to favour political interests, and incentivising short-term and reactive measures rather than integrated, long-term planning. In WASH and climate resilience, where local knowledge and consistent maintenance are very important, these governance patterns take away the effectiveness and weaken the trust of citizens in their local institutions.

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